

IMAGE CLASSIFICATION OF AUTOMOTIVE PARTS: HELICAL GEAR, BEARING, AND WHEEL

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Abstract – This work addresses the classification of three automotive components - wheels, bearings, and helical gears - using computer vision algorithms and deep learning. The dataset, composed of high-quality images, was obtained and reviewed to ensure the model's accuracy, which reached 90%. The system enables precise identification of the parts, contributing to the effective monitoring of components in industrial systems.

Keywords: Computer vision; Deep learning; Classification; Automotive components; Edge Impulse.

INTRODUCTION

The growing automation of industrial processes has driven the development of technological solutions capable of performing complex tasks more efficiently than humans. Among these technologies, machine learning stands out, a field that combines concepts from computer science and statistics to enable machines to learn from data and improve their performance over time [1]. Unlike the human brain, which interprets and reacts to environmental stimuli through a continuous process of learning and adaptation, traditional machines are programmed to perform specific functions without the ability to adapt. Machine learning aims to bridge this gap by empowering systems to analyze data, identify patterns, and make decisions based on previous information [2].

In the industrial context, the classification of visual components plays a crucial role in several sectors, such as automotive, where accurate part identification is essential for the effective maintenance and monitoring of machinery and vehicles [3]. In this project, we address the challenge of classifying three specific automotive components — wheels, bearings, and helical gears — using computer vision algorithms. Supported by a dataset obtained from high-quality images, we aim to create a system that analyzes visual features such as shape, color, and texture to correctly identify each part. Automating this task can not only improve accuracy in identification but also optimize response time in monitoring systems, providing more efficient control of component integrity over time.

The main objective of this project is the classification of images of wheels, bearings, and helical gears, differentiating them. For this purpose, we used a dataset of automotive components available on the Kaggle platform [4],[5] and the neural network generated within the artificial intelligence system of Edge Impulse [6],[7].

DEVELOPMENT

The Automobile-parts-classification dataset by Md Waqar Azamera [8] consisted of approximately 50 high-quality images for each class. These images were reviewed to remove potential learning difficulties, leaving 40 good images per label.

By employing computer vision algorithms, the application can examine images, analyzing characteristics such as coloration, shape, and patterns. This is based on a pre-existing dataset that includes examples of each component chosen for analysis, selected due to their similarities.

The image analysis for classifying these parts can be integrated into real-time monitoring systems, allowing technicians to track the health evolution of the vehicles over time. This enables quick responses to any changes in conditions, ensuring more effective management.

The provided dataset includes photographs taken in the mechanical field, both isolated and grouped, and allocated within automobiles. These images were captured directly in the field and stored in the raw dataset folder. These pre-processing data contain images with a resolution of 256×256 pixels in color scale format.

To build machine learning models, organized and clean deep learning datasets are an essential research requirement. To this end, non-isolated images were removed.

The images are divided into folders to be classified (wheel, helical gear, and bearings) and automatically split by Edge Impulse into 80% for training and 20% for testing, which means an average of 40 images for training and 10 for testing.

This project adopted an image classification approach, which involves using algorithms and techniques that allow a computational system to automatically identify the objects present in an image and assign them to a specific category. This categorization can be based on features such as shapes, colors, textures, and other relevant attributes. To achieve accurate results, pre-labeled datasets are used, where the system learns to associate visual patterns with specific categories.

The application of image classification is particularly valuable in the context of modern mobility, as seen in the specific example of classifying these parts. This approach enables quick and accurate detection of equipment, providing crucial information for professionals to make informed decisions about their management.

The project starts with sets of 45 to 55 images for each category. In the first phase, a configuration of 20

epochs is used, employing the MobileNetV2 architecture with dimensions of 96×96 0.35, 16 neurons, and a dropout rate of 0.1, as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1 – Characteristics of the Neural Network used.

RESULTS E DISCUSSIONS

As illustrated in Figure 2, the model achieved an accuracy of 90%.

Figure 2 – Model results.

We reached an impressive accuracy rate of 90%, with an exceptionally low loss value of 0.22, all in a fast processing time of just 107 milliseconds, as seen in Figure 3. It is notable that our results were nearly perfect when classifying bearings and gears, reaching an outstanding 100% accuracy. However, we observed a drop in performance when dealing with wheel images, where the accuracy was 60%, which ultimately affected the overall project performance, reducing it by 10%.

Figure 3 – Processing time and data volume.

Upon examining the misclassified images, we identified an interesting pattern — most errors occurred in images with grouped sets or the presence of human action in the scene. This suggests that a more thorough review of the database, along with a possible increase in interactions within the neural network, could lead to substantial improvements in our results, allowing us to achieve even more impressive levels of accuracy and efficiency.

CONCLUSION

We achieved the objective and an image classification tool of three automotive components - wheels, bearings, and helical gears – was successfully designed, achieving 90% of accuracy.

The experience with the Edge Impulse platform was extremely positive and enriching. One of the most notable features was the user-friendly and accessible approach the platform offers, especially for those without advanced programming knowledge. The ability to use intuitive tools without the need for direct programming makes artificial intelligence more accessible, allowing even individuals without a specific technical background to take advantage of this technology.

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